

ISic1262

I.Sicily inscription 1262

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2008.09.29

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance

Theatre

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Teatro Greco Romano di Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140750

1. ἱερειᾶν.

2. ἱερε[ι]ᾶν.

3. Φιλιστοῦς δβ'.

4. Φιλιστοῦς δγ' ²⁷δε²⁷.

5. ἱεριᾶ[ν].

6. ἱεριᾶν.

7. NEMEAN

8. Φιλιστοῦ [ς]

9.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492868
EDCS 39101630
PHI 140750

Bibliography

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